

Tough, Self-reporting, Biocomposites using Silk and Nanocellulose Fibers: toughening, interface modification and new multifunctional interface imaging probes

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Abstract

Design of biocomposites, i.e., composites that use at least one bio-derived component, such as silk/epoxy or nanocellulose/epoxy composites, is best accomplished by using nature as a guide. Natural composites are inherently multifunctional; often providing attributes such as: light weight, degradability, strength with flexibility (toughness), sensing and healing, and optical patterning (camouflage). Toughness is accomplished by incorporating toughening mechanisms over multiple length scales and is enabled by exquisite control of the interfacial interactions between the two phases within the *interphase*. The *interphase* is the volume of polymer adjacent to an *interface*, and it can comprise up to 30 volume % of the polymer in a polymer nanocomposite. It controls the effectiveness with which the nanoparticle and polymer interact to produce enhanced properties, but it remains a poorly characterized phase. Specifically, the characterization of dynamics of the polymer in the interphase is necessary to enable intrinsic and extrinsic toughening mechanisms. Measurements capable of probing the interphase on the relevant length scales (1 nm to 200 nm) are necessary to develop the fundamental structure property knowledge needed to create high performance composites.

This presentation will present our efforts to prepare, tough nanocomposites using cellulose nanocrystals in epoxies and block copolymers and self-damage reporting Bombyx mori silk fiber epoxy composites. Furthermore, we will report on the surface modification of the interface in these biocomposites and show how this imparts multifunctionality, and enables direct imaging of the interphase using various fluorescence microscopy tools such as Forster resonance energy transfer, FRET, fluorescence life-time imaging microscopy, FLIM. We will describe the synthesis and surface functionalization methods which have been developed to demonstrate new mechanically-activatable fluorescent probes (mechanophores) and UV/water activatable fluorescent probes (aquafluor).